

Effective Small Object Detection in Remote Sensing Images Based on Improved YOLOv8 Network

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Small object detection has long been a challenging and prominent research area in computer vision. Driven by deep learning, small object detection has made major breakthroughs and has been successfully applied in fields such as national defense security, intelligent transportation, and industrial automation. In our research, we conduct a comprehensive analysis and improvement of the YOLOv8-n algorithm for object detection, and propose two new algorithms. The first algorithm adds an SE Attention module and a detection head for small objects in YOLOv8. Improvements include the following points: a) adding a detection head for small objects to enhance detection capabilities for small objects, b) adding an SE Attention module to the network to improve the detection capability of the model. The resulting algorithm improves the performance of YOLOv8 in small object detection on the remote sensing image DOTA-v2.0 dataset and reduces the interference of noisy data to a certain extent. The second model incorporates the CA attention mechanism into the YOLOv8n model and uses the SEResNeXtBottleneck detection header instead of the YOLOv8n header. Through experimental validation on the DOTA v1 dataset, our improved model demonstrates a more accurate ability to detect small objects, and the experimental results show that by adding the CA attention mechanism, the model is able to focus more effectively on key regions of the image, thereby improving detection accuracy.

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1. Introduction

Object detection is an important research direction in the field of computer vision and is the basis for other complex vision tasks. It is considered the foundation for solving higher-level vision tasks such as segmentation, scene understanding, object tracking, image description, and event detection. Small object detection has long been a challenging aspect of object detection.

Small objects refer to objects with small imaging sizes. There are usually two ways to define small objects. One is by absolute size. In the COCO [1] dataset, objects smaller than 32×32 pixels are considered small objects. The other

is by relative size. According to the definition of the International Society of Optical Engineering, a small object is an object with an imaging area of less than 80 pixels in a 256×256 pixel image; that is, if the size of the object is less than 0.12% of the original image, it can be considered a small object. Examples of small objects are shown in Figure 1. Bulls and dogs marked in the area in Figure 1 (a) represent regular-sized objects, and cars marked in the area in Figure 1 (b) represent small objects. Compared with regular-sized objects, small objects occupy fewer pixels in the image, have lower resolution, and have weaker feature expression capabilities.

In recent years, the rapid development of deep learning technology has revitalized

FIG. 1: (Color online) Comparison of regular objects (a) and small object (b).

small object detection, making it a research hotspot. However, compared to regular-sized objects, small objects usually lack sufficient appearance information, making it difficult to distinguish them from the background or similar objects. Although deep learning has driven major breakthroughs in object detection algorithms, the detection of small objects remains unsatisfactory. Small object detection is still full of challenges. In satellite remote sensing images, objects such as cars and boats may only have dozens or even a few pixels. Precisely detecting tiny objects in satellite remote sensing images will help government agencies curb drug and human trafficking, find illegal fishing vessels, and enforce regulations prohibiting the illegal transshipment of cargo.

In order to solve the problem of small object detection in remote sensing datasets, many researchers have improved the network models of the Faster R-CNN and YOLO series. Zhang *et al.* [2] proposed a detection approach for aircraft based on Faster R-CNN, called MFRC. Their research used the K-means algorithm to cluster aircraft data in remote sensing images, improved anchor points based on the clustering results, reduced the pooling layer in the network from four layers to two layers, and used the Soft-NMS algorithm to optimize the aircraft bounding box. Zhou *et al.* [3] proposed an improved detection algorithm, YOLO-SASE. This approach takes

super-resolution reconstructed images as input and combines the SASE module, SPP module, and multi-level receptive field structure. The number of detection output layers is adjusted by exploring feature weights to improve feature utilization efficiency. Gong *et al.* [4] proposed a novel concept called the fusion factor to control the information that deep layers deliver to shallow layers, adapting FPN to tiny object detection. Their results show that configuring FPN with a proper fusion factor allows the network to achieve significant performance gains over the baseline on tiny object detection datasets. Bosquet *et al.* [5] introduced STDNet and ConvNet as approaches for identifying tiny objects smaller than 16×16 pixels based on regional concepts. Ji *et al.* [6] introduced a small object detection algorithm based on YOLOv4, incorporating multi-scale contextual information and a Soft-CIOU loss function. Ren *et al.* [7] introduced an improved algorithm based on Faster R-CNN that sets appropriate anchor points to exploit high-resolution single high-level feature maps by designing a similar architecture employing top-down and skip connections, combined with context information, and introduced a data enhancement method called “random rotation” to further improve the detection performance of small remote sensing objects. Hao *et al.* [8] proposed a vehicle small object detection

algorithm based on residual networks. Based on the original SSD (Single Shot MultiBox Detector) algorithm, a residual network with stronger feature extraction capabilities and fewer parameters can be used to effectively improve the detection accuracy of small objects. Xin *et al.* [9] introduced DIOU-NMS and Alpha-IoU based on the YOLOv5 network structure. The non-maximum suppression in the original YOLOv5 is replaced by non-maximum suppression based on DIOU_Loss, and the original IoU system is replaced by the α -IoU system, significantly improving mAP and accuracy. Wang *et al.* [10] used Wise-IoU (WIoU) v3 as a bounding box regression loss, introduced BiFormer to optimize the backbone network, which improves the model's attention to critical information, and designed a feature processing module named Focal FasterNet block (FFNB), effectively improving the performance of the model.

In terms of small object detection, most of the existing research is based on early mature models such as YOLO and Faster R-CNN. Although these studies have slightly improved small object detection, deep learning is now developing rapidly, with new frameworks and models. As they continue to be created and the hardware becomes more powerful, new and improved models will achieve better performance. As the latest model, YOLOv8 [11] has significant improvements in all aspects, including the ability to handle small objects. By conducting improvement research based on YOLOv8, we may further improve the model's detection accuracy for small objects. Therefore, in this paper, we made two improvements to the YOLOv8n model for small object detection based on remote sensing data.

This article proposes two new algorithms based on modifications of YOLOv8 to improve small object detection tasks. The first algorithm adds an SE Attention module and a detection head for small objects in YOLOv8. Improvements include the following points: a) adding a detection head for small objects to enhance detection capabilities, b) adding an SE Attention module to

the network to improve the detection capability of the model. The resulting algorithm improves the performance of YOLOv8 in small object detection on the remote sensing image DOTA-v2.0 dataset and reduces the interference of noisy data to a certain extent.

The second algorithm incorporates the CA attention mechanism into the YOLOv8n model and uses the SEResNeXtBottleneck detection header instead of the YOLOv8n header. Through experimental validation on the DOTAv1 dataset, our improved algorithm demonstrates a more accurate ability to detect small objects. The experimental results show that by adding the CA attention mechanism, the algorithm is able to focus more effectively on key regions of the image, thereby improving detection accuracy.

2. Attention model and its types

Attention model (mechanism) is a type of neural network architecture that has gained increasing popularity in recent years, particularly in natural language processing and computer vision tasks. The attention mechanism allows the NN-model to focus on certain parts of the input data that are deemed most relevant while ignoring irrelevant or redundant information. This mechanism can significantly improve the performance of neural network, especially when working with large or complex datasets.

The attention mechanism allows the network to focus on significant features of the product image, such as its shape, color, and texture, while ignoring irrelevant background or noise. This can lead to more accurate and efficient object recognition, segmentation, and cropping.

There are three main types of Attention model:

- Squeeze-and-Excitation block (SE) [12];
- Coordinate Attention block (CA) [15];
- Convolutional Block Attention Module (CBAM) [16].

Let us compare the three attention model types (Fig. 2):

(a) Squeeze-and-Excitation block (SE): This module first applies Global Avg Pool to compress the spatial dimensions to produce a 1D feature vector per channel. Two Fully Connected layers then create relationships between the channels, using nonlinearity for activation and a sigmoid function to create weights that are used to re-weight the original feature maps. This approach improves the channel representation but it does not account. SE focuses only on building interdependencies between channels and ignores spatial features [12].

(b) Convolutional Block Attention Module (CBAM): This module develops the idea of SE by introducing separate attention mechanisms for channel and spatial dimensions. Global averaging and maximal pooling is applied first, followed by convolution with ReLU activation for channel weighting. For spatial attention, channel-by-channel pooling and a large convolution kernel (7×7) are used, which allows the model to capture spatial dependencies but does not address the problem of long-range dependencies. CBAM introduces a large-scale convolutional kernel. CBAM uses a large-scale convolutional kernel to extract spatial features, but ignores the problem of long-range dependencies. Although other attention modules without this problem show good results, the number of parameters is too large for application deployment.[16]

(c) Coordinate Attention block (CA): This novel approach offers a solution to the mentioned shortcomings by focusing on both channel and spatial attention. Instead of a single global average, two separate averages on different axes (X and Y) are used to help capture location and orientation information. After concatenation and convolution, these features are combined, then BatchNorm and nonlinearity are applied. Spatial weights are obtained separately for each axis through Conv2d and sigmoid functions, providing more accurate spatial attention given the global context and orientation of the features.[15]

We used YOLOv8 as the basis for our

algorithm. The structure of YOLOv8 is shown in Figure 3.

3. Squeeze-and-Excitation-based YOLOv8 algorithm

The first algorithm is based on YOLOv8 combined with the SE Attention module and the new small object detection head, which can improve the accuracy of the model in detecting small objects. The following two parts are about the principle of the SE Attention module, how it is inserted into YOLOv8, and the structure and concept of the detection head for smaller objects.

The main principle of SE Attention is shown in Figure 4. The SE module first performs a Squeeze operation on the feature map obtained by convolution to obtain channel-level global features, and then performs an Excitation operation on the global features to learn the relationship between each channel and obtain the weights of different channels, and finally multiply them by the original feature map to get the final features.

There are three operations in SE module:

1. Squeeze operation:

- Assume that the input feature map is X and its size is $C \times H \times W$, where C is the number of channels, H and W are the height and width respectively.
- In the Excitation operation, we use a fully connected layer and a nonlinear activation function to learn the weight of each channel and capture the relationship between channels.
- Mark the feature vector after the pooling operation as $Z \in \mathbb{R}^C$, where Z_C represents the compression feature of the channel C .

2. Excitation operation:

- In the Excitation operation, we use a fully connected layer and nonlinear

FIG. 2: Comparison of attention model types: (a) Squeeze-and-Excitation block, (b) CBAM, (c) Coordinate Attention block.

activation function to learn the weight of each channel to capture the relationship between channels. Assume that the parameters of the fully connected layer are $W_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{C' \times C}$ and $W_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{C \times C'}$, where C' is a smaller dimension.

- Input the feature vector C into a fully connected layer: $Y_1 = \sigma(W_1 Z)$, where σ represents the nonlinear activation function (ReLU).
- Input the output Y_1 of the fully connected layer to another fully connected layer: $Y_2 = \sigma(W_2 Y_1)$, where σ represents the nonlinear activation function (Sigmoid).
- The resulting output $Y_2 \in \mathbb{R}^C$ represents the weight vector of each channel.

3. Scale operation:

- Apply the learned weight vector Y_2 to each channel on the input feature map X .
- For each channel X , multiply its corresponding feature map X_c and the weight Y_{2c} to obtain the weighted feature map: $X'_c = X_c \cdot Y_{2c}$.

- Recombine all weighted feature maps to obtain the final output feature map X' .

The process of the entire SE module can be expressed as: $X' = \text{Scale}(X) = X \cdot \text{sigmoid}(W_2 \text{ReLU}(W_1 \cdot \text{Pool}(X)))$ where Pool represents the global average pooling operation, ReLU represents the ReLU activation function, and sigmoid represents the sigmoid activation function. This formula can be automatically back propagated for training, adjusting the values of W_1 and W_2 gradient descent to optimize the performance of the model. By learning the weight of each channel, the SE module can adaptively adjust the feature map.

In essence, the SE module performs attention or gating operations in the channel dimension. This attention mechanism allows the model to focus more on the channel features with the most information and suppress unimportant channel features. Additionally, the SE module is versatile, meaning it can be embedded into existing network architectures. Figure 5 illustrates how SE Attention is integrated into the C2f or Conv module.

For the addition of small object detection heads in YOLOv8, we only need to pay attention

FIG. 3: (Color online) Structure of YOLOv8 [13].

FIG. 4: (Color online) A Squeeze-and-Excitation block.

FIG. 5: The schema of the original module (left) and the SE module (right).

to its head structure. For the original YOLOv8, the downsampling multiple is large, and it is difficult to learn the learning information of small objects with deeper feature maps. Therefore, we add a small detection head, which can make YOLOv8 pay more attention to the characteristics of small objects and enhance the detection accuracy of small objects. The original three detection feature map sizes are 80×80 , 40×40 and 20×20 , which correspond to the three detection heads that can detect objects with sizes above 8×8 , 16×16 and 32×32 pixels. Now we have added a 160×160 detection feature map, which is used to detect objects above $4 \times$ pixels. Smaller detection pixels can extract more features about small objects.

In the head part of YOLOv8, we have added an additional object detection head to achieve better detection results for small objects. Figure 6 shows how to add a small object detection head structure to the YOLOv8 head structure. The red box indicates the newly added structure.

FIG. 6: The structure after adding a new detection head.

4. Coordinate-attention-based YOLOv8 Algorithm

We improved YOLOv8 by incorporating Coordinate attention and build YOLOv8n-CA-OBB_SEResNeXtBottleneck model. In the YOLOv8n backbone we replace the Detect header with the SEResNeXtBottleneck detection header to improve the detection performance and accuracy of the model. The improved model is shown in Figure 7.

The CA attention mechanism, named C2f_CA in our model structure, is used to replace the C2f module in the original YOLOv8n model (Figure 7).

The Detect header in YOLOv8n plays the role of image detection and recognition, but the recognition rate of small targets is very slow in complex environments. Therefore, we propose the SEResNeXtBottleneck for YOLOv8n,

FIG. 7: (Color online) Improved YOLOv8n-CA-OBB_SEResNeXtBottleneck network structure.

which combines the features of SENet[12] and ResNeXt[16] and integrates the SE module into the structure of the ResNeXt bottleneck. This approach utilizes the features of the ResNeXt header to increase the breadth and expressiveness of the network and improves the understanding of the SEResNeXtBottleneck through the channel mechanism of the SE module.

5. Training Data

In our experiments, we used the DOTA dataset, a large-scale dataset for object detection in aerial images. The dataset is designed to address a range of object detection tasks in aerial imagery, including but not limited to small object detection, dense object detection, and large-scale variation [14]. It can be used to develop and evaluate object detectors in aerial images. We used both DOTA v1 and DOTA v2 in our

FIG. 8: (Color online) Structure of SEResNeXtBottleneck head in the model.

experiments.

The DOTA_{v1} dataset contains over 2,800 images and annotation information for more than 188,000 object instances. The images are collected from different sensors and platforms. Each image ranges in size from 800×800 to $20,000 \times 20,000$ pixels and contains objects exhibiting a wide variety of scales, orientations, and shapes. There are 15 different categories of objects, including airplanes, ships, tanks, baseball fields, tennis courts, basketball courts, sports fields, harbors, bridges, large vehicles (such as trucks and buses), helicopters, swimming pools, football stadiums, roundabouts, and small vehicles [17].

DOTA-v2.0 includes more images from Google Earth, GF-2 Satellite, and aerial sources. It features 18 common categories (planes, helicopters, ships, cars, playgrounds, etc.), 11,268 images, and 1,793,658 instances. The 11,268 images of DOTA are split into training and validation sets. To avoid the problem of overfitting, the proportion of the training and validation sets is smaller than the test set. The training set contains 1,830 images and 268,627 instances, while the validation set contains 593 images and 81,048 instances [17].

Figures 9 and 10 illustrate the types of objects that can be detected in this dataset, along with the instances of each type of object.

As evaluation metrics, we used F1 score, mean Average Precision (mAP), number of

parameters (Params), giga floating point operations per second (GFLOPs), and frames per second (FPS). The correctness of the model is measured using correctness and completeness scores as baselines, with F1 score and mAP calculated from these scores as the final evaluation metrics.

6. Experimental Results

6.1. Object Detection by SE-based YOLOv8

The experiments were conducted on the AutoDL platform with a NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090 (24,268 MiB). Each experiment was performed for 300 epochs. The experimental results are shown in the table below, and examples of detection are shown in Figures 11 and 12.

The experiments show that when the SE Attention module and a new detection head are added to YOLOv8n, better indicators are achieved in terms of accuracy.

6.2. Object Detection by CA-based YOLOv8

The experiments were conducted on the AutoDL cloud computing platform with the following environment configuration: Python 3.10

FIG. 9: (Color online) A number of each category objects in DOTA-v1.0 (a) and DOTA-v2.0 (b).

FIG. 10: (Color online) Pictures from training set in DOTA-v1.0 (a) and DOTA-v2.0 (b).

(Ubuntu 22.04), PyTorch 2.1.0, CUDA 12.1, GPU RTX 4090 (24GB) x2, CPU 32 vCPU AMD EPYC 9654 96-Core Processor, and RAM. For training, the input image size was 640×640 , and the model was trained using SGD as

the optimization function. The training period (epochs) was 300, the batch size was 18, and the initial learning rate was 0.01. This experiment used the same data enhancement algorithm as the original YOLOv8n algorithm.

FIG. 11: (Color online) Original image, result of YOLOv8n and our method.

FIG. 12: (Color online) Original image, result of YOLOv8n and our method.

Table 1: Comparison results

Detector	mAP50(%)	mAP50-95(%)	Recall(%)
YOLOv8n	29.76	17.54	27.57
YOLOv8n+SE Attention	31.03	18.54	28.28
YOLOv8n+one more head	31.28	18.51	29.69
SE-based YOLOv8	31.99	19.12	29.87

FIG. 13: (Color online) Results of the original image, YOLOv8n and our model.

Figure 13 shows the detection results: the left image is the original image from the DOTAv1 dataset, the middle image is the detection result with YOLOv8n, and the rightmost image is the detection result of the YOLOv8n-CA-OBB_SEResNeXtBottleneck model. According to the comparison of results, our model not only detected more small targets but also improved the detection accuracy of large targets.

Table 2 shows the detection results of our method on the DOTAv1 validation test set after 300 epochs in each model framework of the experimental environment.

Experimental results show that our model outperforms the original YOLOv8n model in both mAP50% and mAP50-95%. Specifically, the model improves its performance from 41.0% to 42.7% at mAP50% and from 24.6% to 25.5% at mAP50-95%, indicating that the added CA attention mechanism and SEResNeXtBottleneck header can significantly enhance model performance.

6.3. Comparative analysis of the proposed models

The obtained results show that the proposed models perform distinctively in small object detection.

SE-YOLOv8 enhances the characterization of channel-dependent features and reduces noise interference in complex backgrounds. By

integrating the SE attention module and small-object detection head, it significantly improves the accuracy of small-object detection while maintaining a smaller number of parameters and faster detection speed, suitable for real-time detection applications.

CA-YOLOv8, on the other hand, combines the CA attention mechanism and the SEResNeXtBottleneck detection head, by simultaneously focusing on spatial and channel information, it significantly improves the detection accuracy, especially in complex backgrounds and high-resolution images, but due to the larger number of parameters, the detection speed is relatively slower, which is more suitable for high-precision requirements of the application scenarios.

Taken together, SE-YOLOv8 performs well in resource-constrained applications and those requiring fast detection, while CA-YOLOv8 has significant advantages in scenarios requiring the highest detection accuracy. These two improved YOLOv8 algorithms achieve improved performance in small object detection tasks through different attention mechanisms and feature extraction methods, demonstrating a broad application prospect in remote sensing image analysis.

Table 2: Comparison results

Model	mAP50(%)	mAP50-95(%)
YOLOv8n	41.0	24.6
YOLOv8n-obb	42.3	24.9
YOLOv8n-SEResNeXtBottleneck head	42.2	24.6
YOLOv8n-CA-OBB	42.1	25.1
YOLOv8n-CA-OBB_SEResNeXt	42.7	25.5

7. Conclusion

This paper proposes two new algorithms based on modification of YOLOv8 to improve small object detection task. The first algorithm adds a SE Attention module and a detection head for small objects in YOLOv8. Our algorithm improves the performance of YOLOv8 in small object detection on the remote sensing image DOTA-v2.0 dataset, and improves the interference of small object detection in noisy data to a certain extent.

The second algorithm incorporates the CA attention mechanism into the YOLOv8n model and using the SEResNeXtBottleneck detection header instead of the YOLOv8n header. Through experimental validation on the DOTAv1 dataset, our improved algorithm demonstrates a more accurate ability to detect small objects, and the experimental results show that by adding the CA attention mechanism, the algorithm is able to focus more effectively on key regions of the image, which improves detection accuracy.

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